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³ The initials of the revising individual in capital letters

Deliverable D6.7

Report on the DSTs used in case studies for developing MR1

25/09/2020

Executive Summary

This document contains a report of the Decision support tools used for developing management recommendations (MRs) in each of the FarFish case studies. These tools have been selected in coordination with the production of the version one of the Management Recommendations for each case study. It continues the work program outlined in Deliverable 6.4 in collaboration with other work packages (WPs) of FarFish, mainly WP1 and WP4. The report shows the first outputs of the satellite work as support of compliance. It also describes in detail the tool developed for assessing stock in data limited method situations, including its implementation and dissemination beyond FarFish and a formal assessment of relevance for stakeholders.

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Abbreviations

AIS	Automatic Identification System
CS	Case Study
DLM	Data Limited Method
DoA	Description of Action
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
ESA	European Space Agency
GFW	Global Fishing Watch
GT	Gross Tonnage
ICCAT	The International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas
ICES	The International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
IOTC	The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission
IUU	Illegal, unreported and unregulated
MPA	Marine Protected Areas
MR	Management Recommendation
NOAA	The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OT	Outcome Target
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
VHF	Very High Frequency
VIIRS	Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite
WP	Work Package
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature

Concepts/definitions

Management Recommendation	In RFMS, the management recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority and operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery.
Outcome Target	Outcome targets (OTs) are specific and measurable requirements that are set by an authority to make management goals operational. An OT is a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B') or a statement of presence or absence of some entity. On the basis of relevant information, this statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time ⁵⁴ . For instance, the management objective that “the fishery should be biologically sustainable” could be expressed in terms of one or more OTs such as ‘Catch < 20 000t; ‘by-catch < 20%’; SSB > 30 000t; ‘a catch reporting system is present’, etc.

1 Introduction

The overall objective of work package six (WP6) in the FarFish project is to develop tools that provide added value, relevance and usefulness in support of management and decision making for the actors involved in each of the case studies (CSs). As described in [FarFish deliverable 6.4](#), the relevance and added value was ensured through a consultation process involving both internal (mainly the partners involved in the implementation of the case studies) and external (mainly regional fishery bodies) actors of FarFish. Partnership with other organizations like NOAA, Global Fishing Watch and Google was also incorporated to the exercise. As described in this report, these organizations have provided data and technical support to develop the tools identified as relevant and with added value by internal and external actors while ensuring technical characteristics that make of them useful tools within the context of the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) applied in FarFish.

As described in the DoA and in [FarFish deliverable 6.4](#), for the tools generated in WP6 to be useful to actors involved in the spiral procedure of applying the RFMS approach, they must accomplish a set of operative characteristics such as:

- 1) Facilitating an equal footing for the technical dialogue of all actors involved.
- 2) Guaranteeing all-actors accessibility by working under open-access schemes.
- 3) Interaction with data, simulation and visualization based on free platforms.
- 4) Tools remaining once the project has ended.

It is described in this report how this is being achieved through the use of free and widely used platforms such as RStudio, Shiny or Google Earth Engine. This effort has also benefitted from the data work carried out in WP2, mainly in [deliverable 2.3](#) and deliverable 2.6*. The work carried out and reported on in this report has made use of these data and it has also helped WP2 by shaping the type and format of the database so that its content is straightforward to use in the tools created for the cases studies and beyond FarFish.

In addition to the creation of these tools, the report also describes the following steps where new knowledge is necessary such as the oceanographic control of fisheries or the exploration of innovative paths as potential tools within the context of artificial intelligence. As part of the self-assessment, and following the recommendations received by external expert reviewers during the 18 months evaluation, the tools are being formally assessed by their users through *ad hoc* surveys. This is expected to result in an improvement along the spiral approach which structures FarFish.

* This deliverable has not been made public yet

2 FarFish Decision Support Tool for Data Limited stocks

Despite the important economic and social role of fisheries worldwide, only 80% of world catches come from species for which current catch levels are sustainable (Costello et al 2012). This number claims for tools able to be applied even in conditions where little data (frequently only catch and more rarely effort) and technical expertise is available. A reference for sustainability is available through these tools to managers even in these conditions of poor data and expertise. Owing to this overall situation, the FarFish data limited tool (FarFish-DLMtool) builds on the methods described in Carruthers et al. (2014) and on DLMtool R package. Although there is a toolkit using this package developed by Carruthers and collaborators, we developed a new version to start a continuous feedback process of modification by following the demands of the CS leaders and stakeholders. The first version in this process was focused on enhancing the data input and on easily linking that data to management procedure testing. This results in an add on which fully complies with the conditions identified as necessary in the introductory section of this report for the tools to be implemented in FarFish: It facilitates the technical dialogue with the all actors involved, it does not demand high technical skills, it is open access at free platforms and it will remain after the project.

The preliminary version of FarFish-DLMtool has two components: An online template for data input that allows to upload the data directly from excel sheets or to write it directly in the template, and a summary and results webpage with different tabs. In one of the tabs, the data available is graphically displayed, another tab provides a diagnostics analysis about the management procedures that can be applied according to data availability, and finally in the last tab, a quota estimation with its corresponding uncertainty for each of the plausible management procedures, is displayed.

This tool has been designed to be used by everyone without needing a deep knowledge to run it, but it is important to remark that some stock assessment background is needed to interpret the results obtained. As a decision support tool, this tool is not automating decision making and it is in no way intended to replace skilled decision-makers.

2.1 First round implementation

2.1.1 Tutorial given to CS and WP leaders (Mindelo, November 2018)

During the second Case Studies and Work Package leaders meeting in Mindelo, a tutorial about the use of the preliminary version of FarFish-DLMtool was given. It was a workshop where all the participants worked with a real data set. It was focused on how to upload the data to the template and how to visualize the data and to interpret the diagnostics on what management procedures could be applied according to data availability.

2.1.2 Tutorial given to scientist, authorities and operators at the 2nd annual meeting (June 2019)

During the second annual meeting in Las Palmas a tutorial of an improved version of the FarFish-DLMtool was given. This improved version had a direct link between the template and the results webpage, and also a more detailed description of the different management procedures were included. The same methodology used in Mindelo was applied here and a feedback on the tool was requested by filling a pre-designed questionnaire.

2.1.3 Three-day course in Mindelo for Case Study leaders planned for November 2019

The CS teams have been in touch with the tool in the two meetings mentioned before. Nevertheless, given that a background on fisheries stock assessment is needed to interpret the tool outputs, a three-day course in Mindelo will be focused on specialized scientist on this topic in each CS. This course intends to give a brief view of the use of different data limited methods understanding the pros and caveats of some of them. It will be focused on how to use the tool, the interpretation of results and the different possibilities according to data availability.

2.1.4 Dissemination about the tool implementation under a co-creation approach

The tool was presented in the Data Limited Methods class of the Aquaculture and Fisheries master of University of Cadiz during the 2018-2019 period and it will be presented again during the 2019-2020 period. In addition, the development of the tool under a co-creation approach is going to be presented in the 2019 ICES Annual Science Conference (Gothemburg, 2019), and in the ICES Workshop on Data-limited Stocks of Short-lived Species (WKDLSSLS, San Sebastian, September 2019, <https://www.ices.dk/community/groups/Pages/WKDLSSLS.aspx>).

2.2 First use in connection with MR1

2.2.1 Feedbacks provided to MR1

The following subsections summarize different Outcome Targets (OT) identified in MR1 and how they could be related to the FarFish-DLMtool.

2.2.1.1 Cape Verde

OT 3.1 A harmonised catch data protocol in place that facilitate improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data.

The data limited tool is not a suitable tool to use with this two species, which stock assessment is carried out regularly by the ICCAT, but there are some bycatch species that can be used within the tool as the Frigate tuna and the Wahoo, that are also important to assess.

2.2.1.2 Senegal

OT 4.1 Make bycatch data available.

Sardinella species and other small pelagics such as West African ilisha (*Ilisha africana*) and bonga (*Ethmalosa fimbriata*) have been identified as important bycatch species in the region. At this point data is being gathered and this is the first step for the tool implementation. The tool would provide data visualization, as well as suitable management procedures according to data availability.

2.2.1.3 Seychelles

It is still necessary to improve bycatch database quality and there is enough information to apply some data limited methods to the Wahoo and the Common dolphinfish in the area.

2.2.2 First round implementation by CS's: Diagnostic on methods implementation according to data availability in connection with MR1

Some key bycatch species were chosen according to their relevance and data availability. These species were the Common dolphinfish and Wahoo in the Indian Ocean and Frigate tuna and Wahoo in the Atlantic Ocean. It was decided to implement the tool for the whole Indian and the whole Atlantic Ocean based on the oceanic nature of these species and the lack of structure for these stocks. Data has been provided by IOTC and ICCAT.

This approach can be further scaled to calculate the Cape Verde and Seychelles population using the catch proportion of these species.

As a first step in the data limited methods implementation, we provide a diagnostic of what management procedures can be implemented with the data available (see table 1-4). A more detailed description of the management procedures available in the tool can be found at <https://dlmtool.github.io/DLMtool/reference/index.html>.

Table 1: Diagnostics table on what Management procedures can be implemented according to data availability for Dolphinfish stock in the Indian Ocean

Code	Name	Type	Description
AvC_MLL	Average Catch with a size limit		An example mixed control MP that uses the average catch output control MP together with a minimal size limit set at the size of maturity.
minlenLopt1	Size limit management procedures		
curE	Current effort	Effort	A reference input control that maintains current effort (subject to fishing efficiency changes)
curE75	75% of Current effort	Effort	A reference input control that maintains 75% of current effort
matlenlim	Length selectivity equal to maturity	Sel.	Fishing selectivity is set according to the maturity curve
matlenlim2	Length selectivity higher than maturity	Sel.	fishing selectivity is set slightly higher than the maturity curve
slotlim	Slot limit	Sel.	Sets a slot limit to control effort.
MRnoreal	Area 1 Marine Reserve with no reallocation	MPA	Sets a marine reserve in Area 1 with no reallocation of fishing effort to area 2
MRreal	Area 1 Marine Reserve with reallocation	MPA	Sets a marine reserve in Area 1 and reallocates fishing effort to area 2
AvC	Average Catch	Catch	Sets TAC as average historical catch
CC1	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is an average historical catches
CC2	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 90% of average historical catches
CC3	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 80% of average historical catches
CC4	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 70% of average historical catches
CC5	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 60% of average historical catches
NFref	No reference point	Catch	A reference MP that sets annual catch to almost zero (0.01)

Table 2: Diagnostics table on what Management procedures can be implemented according to data availability for Wahoo stock in the Indian Ocean

Code	Name	Type	Description
AvC_MLL	Average Catch with a size limit		An example mixed control MP that uses the average catch output control MP together with a minimal size limit set at the size of maturity.
minlenLopt1	Size limit management procedures		
curE	Current effort	Effort	A reference input control that maintains current effort (subject to fishing efficiency changes)
curE75	75% of Current effort	Effort	A reference input control that maintains 75% of current effort
matlenlim	Length selectivity equal to maturity	Sel.	Fishing selectivity is set according to the maturity curve
matlenlim2	Length selectivity higher than maturity	Sel.	fishing selectivity is set slightly higher than the maturity curve
slotlim	Slot limit	Sel.	Sets a slot limit to control effort.
MRnoreal	Area 1 Marine Reserve with no reallocation	MPA	Sets a marine reserve in Area 1 with no reallocation of fishing effort to area 2
MRreal	Area 1 Marine Reserve with reallocation	MPA	Sets a marine reserve in Area 1 and reallocates fishing effort to area 2
AvC	Average Catch	Catch	Sets TAC as average historical catch
CC1	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is an average historical catches
CC2	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 90% of average historical catches
CC3	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 80% of average historical catches
CC4	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 70% of average historical catches
CC5	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 60% of average historical catches
NFref	No reference point	Catch	A reference MP that sets annual catch to almost zero (0.01)

Table 3: Diagnostics table on what Management procedures can be implemented according to data availability for Frigate Tuna stock in the Atlantic Ocean

Code	Name	Type	Description
AvC_MLL	Average Catch with a size limit		An example mixed control MP that uses the average catch output control MP together with a minimal size limit set at the size of maturity.
minlenLopt1	Size limit management procedures		
curE	Current effort	Effort	A reference input control that maintains current effort (subject to fishing efficiency changes)
curE75	75% of Current effort	Effort	A reference input control that maintains 75% of current effort
matlenlim	Length selectivity equal to maturity	Sel.	Fishing selectivity is set according to the maturity curve
matlenlim2	Length selectivity higher than maturity	Sel.	fishing selectivity is set slightly higher than the maturity curve
slotlim	Slot limit	Sel.	Sets a slot limit to control effort.
MRnoreal	Area 1 Marine Reserve with no reallocation	MPA	Sets a marine reserve in Area 1 with no reallocation of fishing effort to area 2
MRreal	Area 1 Marine Reserve with reallocation	MPA	Sets a marine reserve in Area 1 and reallocates fishing effort to area 2
AvC	Average Catch	Catch	Sets TAC as average historical catch
CC1	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is an average historical catches
CC2	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 90% of average historical catches
CC3	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 80% of average historical catches
CC4	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 70% of average historical catches
CC5	Constant catch linked to average catches	Catch	TAC is 60% of average historical catches
NFref	No reference point	Catch	A reference MP that sets annual catch to almost zero (0.01)
SPMSY	Catch-trend MSY MP	Catch	Catch trends reflect depletion and combined with catches can be used to find viable r-K pairs. The OFL is $dep \times (1-dep) \times 2 \times r \times K$

Table 4: Diagnostics table on what Management procedures can be implemented according to data availability for Wahoo stock in the Indian Ocean

Code	Name	Type	Description
minlenLopt1	Size limit management procedures		
curE	Current effort	Effort	A reference input control that maintains current effort (subject to fishing efficiency changes)
curE75	75% of Current effort	Effort	A reference input control that maintains 75% of current effort
matlenlim	Length selectivity equal to maturity	Sel.	Fishing selectivity is set according to the maturity curve
matlenlim2	Length selectivity higher than maturity	Sel.	fishing selectivity is set slightly higher than the maturity curve
slotlim	Slot limit	Sel.	Sets a slot limit to control effort.
MRnoreal	Area 1 Marine Reserve with no reallocation	MPA	Sets a marine reserve in Area 1 with no reallocation of fishing effort to area 2
MRreal	Area 1 Marine Reserve with reallocation	MPA	Sets a marine reserve in Area 1 and reallocates fishing effort to area 2
NFref	No reference point	Catch	A reference MP that sets annual catch to almost zero (0.01)

2.3 Formal feedback by users

2.3.1 Joint work with WP1

A questionnaire to get feedback on the tool was designed together with WP1, therefore attending to the request of the external reviewers during the 18-month review as well as the philosophy of the co-creation approach where stakeholders feedback is a key component. This feedback allows to include suggestions during the process of tool development thus enforcing trust as well as motivating users to participate. The questionnaire follows from evaluation frameworks for decision support tools applied before in different EU funded projects (MareFrame (D7.5), EcoFishMan, 2015; MEFEPO, 2017; MyFish, 2017; MEECE (D5.2), 2012). Particularly, the framework developed in the EU project MEECE was suitable to evaluate this tool, with a distinction between system characteristics and context specific criteria (See Deliverable 5.2, MEECE, 2012) where “system” refers to the tool itself. It focuses on what the system technically does, i. e. what it can or cannot do and what is included or not. The concept of “context” refers to the interactions between groups and individuals that are involved in creating, implementing and using the tool. The questionnaire used this framework to evaluate how the tool can be used, and it also has an emphasis on their generic

capabilities. The questionnaire was developed following five main criteria (see Table 5 for the detailed evaluation template):

- Relevance
- Accessibility
- Transparency
- Suitability and purpose
- Adaptability and flexibility

The outcome of this questionnaire will feed into the work conducted in WP6, as well as the subsequent deliverables D6.8, D6.9 and D6.10 that rely on the use of the tool at CS's level.

Table 5: FarFish DLMtool feedback questionnaire provided to FarFish second annual meeting assistants

FarFish DLM tool			
Objective of the tool		Visualization of data available and estimation of the quota according to different management procedures	
Role		Authority <input type="checkbox"/> Operator <input type="checkbox"/> International <input type="checkbox"/> Scientist <input type="checkbox"/> NGO <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/>	
		Low=1 Medium=2 High=3	Additional Description
Relevance	Q1: To what extent can the tool explore and compare management alternatives?		
	Q2: To what extent can the tool allow to visualize the data available?		
	Q3: To what extent the tool allows to identify the data needed for better fishery diagnostics?		
Accessibility	Q4: How effectively are the results summarized and displayed?		
	Q5: How much support is there for users using the tools (in the form of contact persons, user guides etc.)		
	Q6: To what extent is the tool accessible and easy to use for end-users		

Transparency	Q7: To what extent does the tool make visible the levels of uncertainty of the results		
	Q8: How transparent is the tool considering complexity of formulas/models?		
Suitability & purpose	Q9: To what extent can the tool be used for participatory processes?		
	Qu10: To what extent can the tool be used for educational and training purposes?		
	Qu11: To what extent your institution would attend workshops to improve the use of the tool?		
	Qu12: To what extent you would recommend the tool for stock assessment objectives?		
Adaptability & flexibility	Qu13: To what extent is it possible to adjust the tool to needs of different users?		
	Qu14: How flexible is the tool for application in other contexts (e.g. another region)		
	Qu15: What level of application and utility you give to the tool for the evaluation of fisheries of your interest		

2.3.2 Implementation round in Las Palmas de Gran Canarias: Stakeholders feedback results.

After the tool tutorial given to the assistants of the FarFish second annual meeting in Las Palmas, the questionnaire was provided to them. The summary of their answers by question is displayed in Figure 1. In this figure it can be observed that high (3) and medium (2) attributes represent more of the 71% of the population surveyed in all the statements, nevertheless the trends for some specific statement are better represented in the heat map (Figure 2) where it can be observed that the statements with best perception are the statements 2, 4, 10 and 14 with 68.75%, 60%, 66.67% and 60%, respectively, corresponding to data and results visualization, and, suitability for training purposes and use in other contexts. The statements with a higher perception on a medium level are the 6 and 13, with 62.5% and 66.67%, respectively, corresponding to accessibility and flexibility. The overall mean (grey column) for all the statements is better than or equal to 2, where higher means (over 2.4) correspond to statements 2, 4, 9, 10, 11 and 14. Here we remark the general good perception on statements 9 (2.4%) and 11 (2.43%) that were not representatively high in none of the

attributes and that correspond to the suitability of the tool to be used in participatory processes and the motivation of the participants to attend to tool use training workshops.

Grouping results according to the five criteria reveals that the lower score corresponds to the transparency criteria while the higher score corresponds to “suitability and purpose”. Transparency has been measured against how uncertainty is presented, and how transparent the tool is in relation to the complexity of the information included in the tool. In other words, whether it is made clear to the user, what kind of data is presented and the underlying data that provides the results. On the other hand, “suitability and purpose” addresses the suitability of the tool to support participatory processes, and how suitable are the tools for educational purposes.

Figure 1: FarFish-DLMtool feedback questionnaire results by question. Each bar represents the percentage of the population that scores each question with 1 (low), 2 (medium) or 3 (high), respectively. Population: 16 FarFish members after receiving a tutorial on how to use the tool on the second annual meeting.

Figure 2: Heat map summarizing the FarFish-DLMtool feedback questionnaire results by question (each row). The first column displays the mean and Standard deviation. Second, third and fourth columns show the percentage of the population that scores each question with 1 (low), 2 (medium) or 3 (high), respectively. Population: 16 FarFish members after receiving a tutorial on how to use the tool on the second annual meeting.

Figure 3: Average score mean by questions category

The most representative groups in the survey correspond to “Scientist” and “Operators”, which correspond to the 81.25% (13 people) of the total number of participants (16 people). Scientist in the FarFish project are present in all the case studies and also in all work packages while operators are related to both but in an indirect manner, “operators” are those who develop a management plan, undertakes fishing operations according to the pre-set objectives, and provide proof of achieving these objectives through a documentation system (Santiago et al. 2015). Reducing the sample to these two groups only and weighting them accordingly to have both the same weight regardless of the number of members, show that operators gave a lower punctuation than scientist for most of the statements (Figure 4). Exceptions are for number 11 (where is higher) and 13 (where is equal), the first one corresponds also to the highest score given by the “Operators” (2.33) group and it reveals that they are a little bit more motivated than scientist to attend to training workshops, which is very interesting considering that they used to be in lesser contact with these kind of tools than scientists. The second one is about the flexibility of the tool to be adapted to the needs of the different users, where both groups have in average the same perception, for instance this is the lowest average score provided by the scientist group. The higher scores given by the scientist group corresponds to statements 2 (2.8), 10 and 14 (2.67) remarking that the tool allows to visualize the data available, the suitability of the tool for training purposes and flexibility to be applied in other context, respectively, “operators” group gave also the highest score to these statements but with lower punctuation (2.33) compared to the other group. Operators also gave the highest score (2.33) to statements 4 and 9, about the ease to display and summarize the results and the suitability of the tool for participatory processes, respectively, and also to the statement 11 as described before. The lowest score given by this group (1.0) corresponds to statement 3 about the capacity of the tool to identify the data needed for better fishery diagnostics which reflects some misunderstanding from this group about the components of the tool because it has an explicit tab where the data needed for better diagnostics is displayed. This shows that there is a need of more training on the use of the tool and this is supported by the general good perception about the suitability of the tool for training purposes (66.67% of the population assign the highest score to this question) and the

participants motivation to attend to training workshops. In addition, there is not a good perception (28.57% of the population assign the lowest score to this question) about the use of the tool for stock assessment, which demand from us a better specification on the users and purpose of the tool and the need to set a warning requiring previous training on the tool or enough knowledge on stock assessment methods.

Figure 4: FarFish-DLMtool feedback questionnaire results by question restricted only to scientist and operators (13 individuals of 16). Bars represent the weighted mean and are displayed with their corresponding confidence intervals

Operators giving a lower punctuation than scientist for most of the statements reflects again the difficulty of conciliate both points of view (Mackinson et al. 2011, Ramirez-Monsalve et al. 2015) and according to Mackinson, S., & van der Kooij, J. (2006), “It reasons that differences of opinion are rooted in alternative perspectives, both entirely understandable and valid within their windows of observation.”

These results remark the importance of enhance the tool as a communication link between both groups, and it encourages us to continue with this feedback process. The three-day course in Mindelo for CS leaders planned for November 2019 could help to address those differences, at some extent, by allowing operators to participate and it will answer to the training need that clearly arises in this feedback while supporting the MR2 development.

Another feedback session is planned during the course, including open ended questions to the questionnaire.

3 Satellite and big data tools in support of compliance

3.1 Technical description of the tools implemented

Unofficial estimations by WWF of the IUU fish going into the EU market raise the number to 11-26 million of tons, about 15% of the European market. High seas are particularly vulnerable to IUU since regulation and compliance control is less strict in those waters under no direct control of a national authority. In many cases, the national authorities closer to the high sea area have difficulties even to provide *in situ* control to ensure compliance in their EEZ waters. Therefore, high seas areas, including vast sea regions, are frequently under the need of more compliance control owing to insufficient *in situ* resources. These limitations for *in situ* control of EEZ and non-EEZ waters make particularly attractive alternatives based in the sensing of human activities at sea by making use of advances in satellite technology.

3.1.1 Global Fishing Watch

One of the satellite technologies which has impacted more to the maritime community over the last few years has been the possibility to make use of the existing infrastructure of low orbiting communication satellites to capture and store AIS (Automatic Identification System) information of professional vessels. The AIS system was designed for VHF inter-boat transfer of information, mainly to prevent collisions, therefore not depending on satellites for the communication among vessels. The system is based in the regular transmission of a VHF message which includes the position, velocity and characteristics of the vessel among other pieces of information of the emitting boat. The 2002 IMO SOLAS Agreement included a mandate that required most vessels over 300GT to fit an AIS transceiver. In addition to this agreement, many countries have state regulations forcing the installation of AIS transceivers for vessels involved in commercial activities. It is estimated that about 250,000 vessels have fitted an AIS transceiver in 2012 with a number of one million to be reached in the near future.

While AIS has been deployed globally, it suffers from a major limitation which is shared by all VHF communications. Earth's curvature limits its horizontal range to about 74 km from shore. This means that AIS traffic information is available only around coastal zones or on a ship-to-ship basis. Tracking ships using satellites overcomes this since vessel AIS message is recorded and decoded by satellites, then sent to ground stations for further processing and distribution (Figure 5). ESA is promoting satellite-based AIS (S-AIS) services in partnership with the European Maritime Safety Agency thus supporting the European Commission and Member States in the prevention, among other activities, of the pollution from ships as well as the tracking of dangerous goods.

Figure 5: AIS system

As part of the new potentials emerging from the satellite services associated to AIS, a new organization has emerged (Global Fishing Watch, GFW) which is promoting the use of this technology for increasing the control of IUU fisheries. GFW is a consortium including Oceana, an international organisation dedicated to protecting and restoring the ocean; SkyTruth, experts in using satellite technology to protect the environment; and Google, who provides the tools for processing big data. The activities of GFW are meaning an enormous step in the transparency of fishery information, not only because the organization provides near real-time tracking of more than 65,000 fishing vessels via their public map but also because they interact and give access to their raw data to projects, such as FarFish, willing to use this massive information for scientific research. Through activities in WP6, FarFish has established partnership with GFW and this has allowed the project to have access to more than 4 GB of data which includes daily data of effort of individual vessels along the whole ocean for the period between 2012 and 2019.

Despite the new power that has emerged from the global tracking of vessel position, there are drawbacks in the system implemented in GFW. These have been pointed out by other maritime organizations such as Windward (wnwd.com). This organization is alerting that vessels engaging in illegal activities are gaming the system and manipulating AIS data. Windward is detecting this manipulation since 2012 when organizations like GFW, or others like MarineTraffic, started to openly offer massive AIS data. Windward assessment is pointing to facts like 1% of IMO numbers transmitted by AIS are fake or their estimation of the Chinese fishing fleet being responsible of 44% of all GPS manipulations. Windward main critic to the GFW products is that their program is only watching the vessels that want to be watched. Moreover, despite the algorithms developed by GFW to detect erratic AIS transmission, a symptom of GPS manipulation, Windward considers that crews are becoming savvier to the various AIS manipulations they can make in a learning curve that improves their capacity for not being detected.

Therefore, despite the unquestionable utility of the database generated by GFW, for a more complete implementation to compliance purposes, this needs to be complemented with alternative sources of information, either *in situ* or through remote sensing. FarFish is exploring two alternative sources of information obtained through satellite: VIIRS and VMS data.

3.1.2 VIIRS

Remote sensing from satellites has had an enormous progress in the last decades, with a very significant increment in the time, space and spectral resolution for the monitoring of the ocean. Available tools for the surveillance of human activities are, however, more limited. The large increment of space resolution achieved by missions like Deimos-1 or Sentinel-2 allow the direct observation of vessels in the ocean. However, this is not yet accompanied by enough frequency of observation to be routinely used for the control of compliance. More important for FarFish aims, the processing of Deimos-1 or Sentinel-2 images is complex and demands highly specialized expertise; thus, not accomplishing the technical characteristics identified in the DoA for the tools to develop in WP6.

However, there is a new generation of instruments without the spatial resolution of Deimos-1 or Sentinel-2 but designed to be highly sensitive to low radiance levels. One of these instruments is the radiometer for visible infrared VIIRS (Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite) on board of Suomi NPP, which is part of the system for earth observation of NASA. The spatial resolution of VIIRS is about 750 meters and it offers a daily coverage of the earth. One of VIIRS spectral channels is DNB (Day Night Band), specifically designed to capture low light levels during the night (Figure 6). The sensitivity of DNB is enough to capture the light of some fishing vessels while operating their gear at sea.

Figure 6: Picture of Radiometer VIIRS on board Suomi NPP (left) and VIIRS night picture of western Europe (right)

3.1.3 VMS

The vessel monitoring system (VMS) is a standard tool of fisheries monitoring and control worldwide. It was the EU which led the way, becoming the first part of the world to introduce compulsory VMS tracking for all the larger boats in its fleet. The EU legislation requires that all coastal EU countries should set up systems that are compatible with each other, so that countries can share data and the Commission can monitor that the rules are respected. The system is compulsory for EU vessels above 15 m (as from 1 January 2012 – vessels above 12 m). VMS is also compulsory for EU vessels involved in fishing activities of non-EU waters.

VMS is the definitive control tool, but it is also subject to limitations since it may involve the processing of protected data. Despite being a very solid source of information to contrast compliance, data rights under specific privacy statements limit its distribution by those organizations having access to them. Consequently, availability, therefore transparency, of this source of information is not as high as other sources such as AIS or radiometer data. As a research project, FarFish is in the process of requesting this information from several sources with limited success so far.

3.2 Visualization tool for GFW, VIIRS and VMS data connected to FFDB

An interactive tool has been developed to visualize the GFW data available (now it is stored in FFDB), further development of this tool includes the comparison with other information sources, such as VIIRS or VMS data to assure compliance. The tool is carefully described in D6.5.

3.3 Open and transparent access to the tool: Google Earth Engine

As identified in the DoA, in addition to relevance and added value, the tools generated by FarFish must include a set of technical characteristics to be useful in the implementation of a Responsive Fisheries Management System, namely:

- 1) Platforms to host the tools will be free and open access to guarantee reproducibility, interoperability, affordability, and transparency.
- 2) The tools will ensure full access to all actors in the process.
- 3) The tools will ensure the immediate capacity of all actors to use it once this has been created.
- 4) Sustainability once FarFish project is finished.
- 5) The codes generated will be implemented within open code platforms.

These technicalities are more difficult to achieve when the tool is based on the use massive data obtained from satellites. However, FarFish is not the only initiative facing the need to increase transparency and accessibility to analysis of big data connected to earth functioning and its natural resources. Powerful organizations like Google have already implemented platforms to facilitate this aim and FarFish is making use of this, concretely of Google Earth Engine.

Google Earth Engine is a cloud-based platform that makes it easy to process very large geospatial datasets. Additionally, Google Earth Engine is also designed to easily disseminate the results of the analysis to policy makers, NGOs, field workers, and even the general public. Algorithms developed on Earth Engine can be transformed into systematic data products or applications backed by Earth Engine's resources, without needing to be an expert in application development, web programming or HTML. Therefore, the Earth Engine is a platform matching the technical conditions imposed by FarFish for the tools, in particular for those making use of massive satellite data like GFW or VIIRS.

FarFish is already applying Google Earth Engine for the analysis of satellite information in case studies with tool codes that will be open to the public for the use in the cases studies as well as outside the FarFish consortium. The system is composed of the following components:

- Data set from VIIRS images and GFW program.
- Computational power provided by Google online.
- Application Programming Interface (API) with a programming library provided by Google.
- Code editor provided by Google and codes created in this work package for the analysis of interest to the case studies and FarFish aims.

3.4 Case study implementation

FarFish has already implemented Google Earth Engine in conjunction with GFW dataset and VIIRS available images to test its suitability for assessing compliance from the space. The CS selected is the southwest Atlantic, a high-sea fishery where *in situ* surveillance is less feasible thus more prone to illegal practices. In particular, a first test has been conducted to assess the possible manipulation of GPS data to avoid AIS tracking of these activities. Figure 7 shows the VIIRS composite image for the whole period of study (2012 to 2018). In addition to the urban areas of South America, the image also evidences the massive presence of fishing activities beside and outside the EEZ of Argentina. This was clustered in three regions, with R1 in the map tagging the main activity conducted in high seas in connection with the fishing of *Illex argentinus* stock.

Figure 8 shows a preliminary assessment of R1 obtained with Google Earth Engine over the dataset provided by GFW for the region. The figure shows the fishing hours accumulated each month in R1 of

Figure 7. It is evident the progressive increment of effort over the years detected by satellite AIS data provided by GFW. This increment does not support, at least for this fishery, the claim by maritime organizations like Windward in the sense that GFW data are too heavily distorted by GPS manipulation after 2012 to not be reliable for the assessment of compliance in fisheries activities. Further insight into this can be obtained by analysing VIRRS proxy for effort in R1. This proxy is the radiance (in relative units) accumulated each month in R1 of Figure 8, as shown in Figure 9. It is worth to emphasize that GFW and DNB at Figure 8 and Figure 9 are completely independent sets of data, coming from completely independently sources and technologies. Although the assessment is still underway, the coincidental pattern between Figure 8 and Figure 9 seems to add credibility, at least for this fishery, to the GFW database as a compliance tool. The coincident pattern also shows the feasibility of using contrasting and independent remote sensing technologies for the redundant surveillance of fishing activities in areas where in situ vigilance is more difficult.

Figure 7: Map showing Southwest Atlantic fishing area for *Illex argentinus*. R1, R2 and R3 are the regions analysed with DNB and GFW data.

Figure 8: Fishing hours accumulated each month in R1 of Figure 7 obtained from GFW dataset

Figure 9: Radiance (in relative units) accumulated each month in R1 of Figure 9

4 Progress towards new tools: New knowledge support to MR1

4.1 Innovative artificial intelligence tools for stock assessment

The strategy of model construction is a critical step in the management of ecosystems and their services. Selecting among a set of state variables, parameters and functional relationships is usually performed with the explicit goal of maximizing both data fitting and the predicting capacity (Clark 2007 Models for ecological data, Getz et al. 2018 *Ecol Lett*, 21: 153-166), being the latter essential for decision taking in managing. Therefore, beyond the heuristic value of the approach, in the exploitation of renewable resources, model adequacy is usually evaluated in terms of its predictive capacity (Power *et al.*, 1993; Getz *et al.*, 2018).

This capacity is key to develop strategies for the sustainable managements of fish stocks under the assumption that present biomass conditions future recruitment (Myers, 1996). The mathematical representation of the link between stock biomass and subsequent recruitment dates back to the first models of fished populations by Ricker (Ricker, 1954) and Beverton-Holt (Beverton, 1957). These functional representations are still the basis for making decisions on many stocks worldwide as they nominally allow calculating a sustainable yield while exploiting the stock (Troadec, 1983). However, extensive analysis of numerous stocks has evidenced that both Beverton-Holt and Ricker equations frequently fail as predictors of fish recruitment, which questions the management strategies based on them (Cury, 2014).

As an alternative to these limitations, phenomenological models represent the opposite extreme to assuming a given SR relationship seized to a particular analytical form. They neither assume nor look for the mathematical expressions connecting the stock with the subsequent recruitment. This is possible within the framework of empirical dynamic modelling, which uses attractor reconstruction as a predictive tool (Sugihara, 1994). However, the ability to predict recruitment from stock biomass seems relatively poor with this approach. A worldwide assessment of this skill in stocks from the RAM legacy and ICES databases suggests that, for most of the stocks analysed, selecting the value of recruitment in the previous year as the predictor (a naive predictor) outperforms forecasts based in empirical dynamic modelling (Pierre et al., 2018). Without an analytical form or an increased prediction capacity as output, the analysis by Pierre et al. seems to indicate that the present state of these tools still needs more progress to help in our understanding of stock-recruitment relationships. Therefore, they are not yet in a state of maturity enough to be consistent with the technical characteristics identified for the tools to be developed (Introduction section of this report).

Given the limitations of completely seizing and entirely disregarding the analytical form linking stock and recruitment, FarFish has explored symbolic regression as an intermediate path between

completely seizing and entirely disregarding the analytical form linking stock and recruitment. This is an innovative approach since, to our knowledge, symbolic regression has not yet been implemented in applied fisheries research. Despite its very innovative nature, symbolic regression fulfils many of the technical characteristics identified for FarFish tools thus deserving to be explored for the pool of gadgets developed within FarFish.

Symbolic regression (or symbolic function identification) has shown its capacity to extract the analytical form underlying cause and effect relationships in nature from observed data alone (Rudy, 2017). Symbolic regression explores a function space of preselected mathematical operators and operands under a genetic algorithm while evaluating the candidates in its ability to match observations with simple expressions (Schmidt, 2009). As part of machine learning methods, symbolic regression shares the flexibility of implementation with other artificial intelligence techniques such as neural networks. However, it is different in that it produces interpretable models with a precise analytical form (Quade, 2016). Importantly, in contrast to the classical approaches used to assess the SR relationship, through symbolic regression the analytical form is not the start but the final product in the assessment process.

The potentials of symbolic regression as one of the tools to be provided by FarFish is being now assessed by making use of the Ram Legacy database which includes stocks covering different basins of the world ocean. In coherence with the DoA, the tools to run the genetic algorithm will be GPTIPS2 package (Searson, 2015) which is freely available. The assessment is including an analysis of the performance of symbolic regression for predicting the recruitment once the value of the stock is known. This exercise is being conducted in comparison with classical approaches such as Beverton-Holt or Ricker, to explore if additional prediction capacity can be developed thanks to the power of symbolic regression as a modelling tool.

4.2 Differentiation of Black Hake at NW Africa

During the consultation described in [Deliverable 6.4](#), it was demanded the creation of tools to differentiate hake stocks in NW Africa. This subject has been extensively analysed by FarFish consortium who has made use of the close contact with the sector thanks to the work conducted in WP1. Together with the CS members who demanded this, it has been concluded that the added value for this particular topic can be obtained in synergy with the self-sampling program to be developed together with the sector in WP2. The collaboration of the sector facilitates the precise geolocation of the specimen to be analysed and the genetic analysis the unquestionable differentiation between species. FarFish is investing in this effort that will provide for the first time a genetic analysis and maps of hake in NW Africa thanks to the self-sampling program developed in WP2.

4.3 Environmental forcing of small pelagics in NW Africa

New scientific knowledge was also demanded to understand how environmental forcing creates fluctuation of small pelagics in NW Africa. The exploratory work for this scientific contribution has already started in close collaboration with Cadi Ayyad University in Marrakesh to develop the knowledge where small pelagic dynamics in Mauritania can be understood in the oceanographic frame of the region and where vulnerabilities can be assessed. The procedure to follow in the coming months will follow the steps already implemented for small species in the past (Ruiz et al. 2017) during the MareFrame EU Project, with similar expected outputs as tools for the involved actors.

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